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“FADING LIGHTS”

In the land where gawking eyes are blind
Scorched by war's unyielding hand,
Where hunger gnaws like grains of sands,
Two small souls wander through fading lights,
Lost their mom and dad,
In this tragic life of war.

My brothers' fierce eyes,
And my sisters' soft touch
Together holding hands
In the mist of this strings of life.

As they walk from place to place
Corpses lay in there
Resting place
No names, just remains
Of their ones breathing markings

My sisters held my hand so tight
Tears looming in her eyes
Scared and grief-stricken
Thinking it would be our mom and dad.

We look for our living families
In a far distant land.

We found one,
But hostility is rigid
Shown in their glooming faces
Two more mouth to feed
Is a burden to live.

How can we survive
if mom and dad is not alive?
Two wandering souls, hoping to live.

My brother is ten,
And my loving sister like a baby
longing for our dear mommy.

Food is scarce
Home is long gone.
Soft bed becomes hay,
Bombs drop like a midnight sun
Trembling, thundering, echoing, waiting.
To catch another soul to mourn
In the darkness of the night.

My brother and sister learn to laugh,
Even of all the things we lack
As long as we are together
We are abundant.

But there are times when we long for
Our mother gentle song,
Fathers heartily grasp
As we play in our vast land.

As we remember those days,
Heartaches break our heart,
Cos we still need our mom and dad.

In the dead of the night,
My little sisters cried
Hunger twists her face like a frown,
She wraps her arms around my worn-out knees
Crying, pleading needing mom,
Holding you, I hum mothers' gentle lullaby
To sooth your pain
Knowing I can't provide you any medicine
Only my presence
In this distressing pathetic regime.

At some point you stop from crying
Breathing slow, fatigue overcomes me
My young body deep in slumber
In our sorrowful condition.

Before breaking dawn,
I saw you lying
Thinking you were sleeping.

I look for bread and some nutriment
For you to fare
In our dire situation we need to bare.

Happily, I run to our shack
Wondering, why are you not up.
My heart sunk
You are cold and staring blank
My little sister made its farewell,
I scream in despair

A picture of what was,
What could have been
If only I have the medicine
Maybe you are still beside me-
Talking, laughing and giggling.

As my brother digs her grave,
Memories creeps,
My sister asks” Is this where mother and father went?”
Tears falling like the faith of fireflies

My little sisters went,
Laying in the grounds with torn-out garments
With trembling breath
Digging deeps where bombs never hit,
Hiding how much of his hope is death.

Realizing that war leaves no room for gentle things.

In the end, I’m asking myself
How could I live if all them
Is underneath dead.

Grieving, my heath is dying
But I’m still alive
Remembering
In my brightest heaven to
My worst of time
A quiet flame beneath the darkest sky,
That war brings only tears in our eyes.

When morning comes, I visit her again
Resting in her burial ground
"You are with them now,"
Promising to sustain my life
And tell you tales of places far and bright
In every beat of my remaining chest,
Our bond lives one,
Your hands stay curled in mine,
My little sister, in fading light
You are my Luminar.

